

Jupiter – Your Sweet 16

63 Comments / Blog, English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

Pay by Happiness- Every planet has its commodity, and this commodity is allocated based on the quality of the planet.

Such as Moon is emotion, Saturn is Salt, Jupiter is happiness, Mars is energy, Mercury is Speech and humor, Venus is happiness in relationships.

The portfolio of Jupiter is happiness, and this is not a temporary happiness which you get in dasa of Rahu as during the Dasa of Rahu, Happiness and Sadness comes suddenly but during the dasa of Jupiter happiness creeps in slowly like first ray of Sunlight removing all the darkness around you, This is happiness of contentment, This is the dasa when you realize that you don't need anything else in life, Dasa of Guru means your natal Moon has progressed over to nakshatra of Jupiter and now for next 16 years your thoughts and life will be governed by Jupiter, The realm of Jupiter will now have control over your thoughts and whole life will now shape up based on how Jupiter is placed in the chart.

Every one of us live in a different world even when we all are on same plane but all of us have different world, If you don't trust me look around you and think about different family members, your cousins and you will find that you are only syncing with people who are running almost similar dasa as yours, and the moment you meet someone in opposite dasa, without any reason you hate that person as this is not the enmity inside you but enmity of a Graha.

Jupiter is valuable and most important in life as what is valuable for you is not worth anything for Jupiter, A guru is valuable because he don't require anything from you and speaks truth to you, How can you make a person happy whose only work is to lift you up in life and make sure you reaches the stage of liberation. Jupiter in any sign has only objective and that is by using the wisdom and broad mindset, using great thinking abilities to resolve the issues of the house and sign Jupiter is placed, Some of the houses are where Jupiter can freely exercise the freewill and impart wisdom by emotions, while in some houses it becomes difficult for Jupiter to work as Jupiter can provide guidelines, hints and opportunities in its dasa to native to change their habits and rise up in life to achieve the liberation and work for soul development.

Jupiter Dasa- Pay by Happiness, It is Jupiter which gives you happiness in your body, a feeling of contentment, The power of smell and a feeling of that divine inside you due to which you trust anyone, Why Sikhs are so fearless warriors as there is a trust of Guru embedded in them from young age, When you pray the faith inside you gets stronger and there is a lot of determination in your voice and actions to not bow down to anything which is against your principles.

It is dasa of Jupiter when afflicted, you pay by happiness, make critical decisions related to principles in life and for this you need to have trust inside you that what you are doing is absolutely right, It is dasa of Jupiter when mentors come or leave from life and stress becomes part of life.

Jupiter when placed in Saturn sign, is a good time for profession but bad for overall happiness as this time period will be like, you are progressing but physical hardships increases. As now Jupiter will make sure you learn lot of things but from people who are not clean but hardworking and you will be the odd one out in your workplace related to your religion and other spiritual practice, In Dasa of Jupiter in Saturnine signs native travels or shift close to hometown but due to work.

Eating bland food which has a lot of potassium is a good remedy for Jupiter under the influence of Saturn, One of the other remedies is reciting Gajendra Moksha and consuming swarn Bhasam.

Jupiter in Gemini native decides to learn something new and go on for self soul searching and come in contact with people who will become his disciple and form groups and community for learning, This dasa is special for siblings and contacts as due to these people you will get lot of new thoughts and learning, When Jupiter is in Virgo, now work of Jupiter is to teach you how to do argument with a smile and never to lose patience, try out new methods to eliminate enemy and you will learn that its a marathon not a sprint, I have Seen People with Jupiter in Virgo they do not wage a war until and unless they build a proper fort and then create social environment for the enemy that finally the enemy get socially boycotted and in this dasa if this is afflicted due to

punishment native travels to different place, The world of native changes and comes in contact with people who will teach him value of every small action.

When placed in Aries/Scorpio Jupiter starts working on self development and how i can get better, Everyday native try to learn something but due to ego satisfaction and showing who is the boss and this goes out of hand, As Jupiter in Kendra hardly listens to anyone else and this is the time period when Ego needs to be in control, While Jupiter in Scorpio is a dasa of self discovery and this is the dasa when native changes his house, profession and things goverend by Jupiter in individual chart as they have over lived their time and its time to move to new place for closing down various other chapters of life.

Jupiter of Royal signs like cancer and Leo goes on special assignment and changes are due to social upliftment and celebrations, Jupiter in Cancer is the expansion of the horizon for the masses as now you have to travel to different places and land to fullfill the karma of Jupiter and this is the dasa when native changes place for the peace and security to get comforts in life, while in Leo Jup dasa native has to oversee project and be the advisor, this is the dasa when significant events related to kids and position of native happens in life.

Jupiter in Venus signs moves due to money, partners and diseases in family, Jupiter in Venus signs have to be careful as lot of people from opposite sex approaches native in the name of position as a person with Jupiter in taurus is head in a financial institution but also had an affair with someone who was his junior which eventually impacted in his child health, Any karam done in Taurus will come to Leo, Please be careful of what you are doing in life.

Jupiter in Jupiterian signs is in contentment and focuses on internal growth and try to be isolated due to change in work, Jupiter in Saggi teaches how to rise up in life by continuously working hard with principles and honesty and this is the dasa when you will be tested, when you will get new ideas and ideology, You will find people with Jupiter Saggi dasa and how they are on the mercy of the Bhagya, this dasa they get move closed to boss's office and act as eyes and ear for seniors, for someone who is working from home or not in profession, this is the dasa when you should expect a guru coming to your to change your belief system completely and this is the reason why most people go through divorce when a planet is in saggi as the belief changes for the native, Jupiter in Pisces is the final destination when native goes in isolation and try to change place so native can work without restrictions and this dasa is when native do not want any restrictions from anyone in life.

You pay by your happiness index in the Jupiter dasa as the whole agenda of Jupiter is to give you happiness in life and the decisions taken by you are totally based on only one outcome- "IT WILL GIVE ME HAPPINESS" -What happens when you get happy, most people belonging to Rahu domain will go on drinking alcohol as they wish to forget everything which is happening in real world and shut down their brain to reach an animal state to be happy, while the happiness of Jupiter will take you to other side of being human by raising your conscious level by making sure every action done

by you, you think beyond human capability of weather its right or wrong ? you think for others and this is what is work of a Guru to raise your conscious level and make you think deeper in life.

I hope this small article has given you glimpse of Jupiter in life and raise your conscious level- To review please use this link and let me know about your Jupiter dasa- <https://g.page/r/CUeqFFQpOFswEB0/review>

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63 thoughts on “Jupiter – Your Sweet 16”

RICHA

27 JULY 2023 AT 17:47

Thank you for amazing article sir 🙏 .

[Edit](#)[Reply](#)**SAKSHI CHOPRA**

27 JULY 2023 AT 17:49

Sor can you ovide more info on jupiter in libra .

[Edit](#)[Reply](#)**CHANAKYA**

28 JULY 2023 AT 10:45

The native with this placement has options when it comes saying the final yes in relationship.

Such natives don't say no easily to their available options.

Also, Jupiter in Libra native becomes a generator of wealth, if you happen to be in company of a native with Jupiter in Libra, you're likely to get more chances to earn money & wealth.

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